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TO ASSESS THE APPROPRIATE DOSING OF ANTIMICROBIALS, ANTIHYPERTENSIVES AND ORAL HYPOGLYCEMIC AGENTS IN CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE PATIENTS AT TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL: A RETROSPECTIVE, OBSERVATIONAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Background: In patient with renal dysfunction, the renal excretion of the parent drug and its metabolite is already impaired leading to accumulation and toxicity. Also the activities of drug metabolizing enzymes and drug transporter are reduced. In such patients, medication dosing errors become the important Drug Related Problem which needs to be assessed closely. **Objectives:** This study aims at assessment of appropriate dosing of Antimicrobials (AMA), Anti hypertensives (AHA) and Oral Hypoglycemic Agents (OHA) in patients with Chronic Kidney Disease at the tertiary care hospital in India. **Materials and Methods:** A Retrospective, Observational study was conducted for 110 patients at a tertiary care hospital in Surat between Jan, 2020 to Jan, 2021. It included patients diagnosed with CKD stage 3, 4 and 5 who were prescribed with at least one antimicrobial, antihypertensive or oral hypoglycemic agent. Kidney function was estimated from GFR using MDRD equation, and dose appropriateness was determined by comparing practice with relevant reference books. **Results:** For the total 110 CKD patients - 361 drugs were prescribed which included 199 (55.12%) AHA, 53 (14.68%) OHA and 109 (30.19%) AMA. 328 drugs out of 361 were prescribed correctly with dose adjustment as required for all of three classes of drugs with majorly being AMA18 (16.5%), by OHA 04 (7.55%) followed by AHA 03 (1.5%). Overall adjustment was required in 25 prescribed drugs. Apart from these, there were a total 8 contraindicated drugs which were all oral hypoglycemic. **Conclusion:** Our study concludes that, according to individual patient's GFR most of the AHA prescribed were adjusted appropriately whereas some of the AMA required adjustment and few OHA prescribed were contraindicated.

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INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this study is to assess the appropriate dosing of antihypertensives, antimicrobials and oral hypoglycemic agents in CKD patients with stage 3,4 and 5 because the patients diagnosed with CKD require individualization of dosage regimen as CKD has been described as a silent epidemic and it is a worldwide health problem. A national survey in USA has estimated that CKD affects 5% of the adult U.S. population when CKD is defined as Sr. cr. Concentration greater than 1.2-1.5mg/dl.¹ In 2000, approximately 10 million people in U.S. were estimated to have CKD. Among these 10 million, 8 million of population had GFR less than 60mL/min/1.73m². This is the point at which the secondary complications are more prevalent. The major secondary complications are HTN, DM, Cancer, Respiratory disease, infection, Anemia. HTN, DM, Cancer, Respiratory disease co-morbidities alongside CKD have account for 60% of total global deaths. Although HTN, DM is considered as co-morbidities, CKD also has other complex causes. Such disease has an indirect impact on global mortality and morbidity by increasing the risks associated with at least other five major killer diseases i.e. CVD, DM, HTN, infections such as HIV and malaria. The best way to manage CKD and its other major complication is to identify the risk factors as soon as possible and start the therapy with ACEIS and ARB in early stages of CKD. These classes of drugs have protective effect during early stages. ESRD patients have mortality rate up to 4 times higher as compared to normal patients at age of 65 or older. The associated predictors of mortality at the start of dialysis include a lower estimated GFR, decreased serum albumin, and the presence of co-morbidities such as HTN, DM.² According to the GBD 2015 study, 1.2 million people died from kidney failure. These study states there was increase of 32% since 2005. In 2010, an estimated of 2.3-7.1 million people died without proper access to dialysis. With addition to this a total of 1.7 million people are thought to die from acute kidney injury. The estimated number of DALYS attributable to kidney disease globally increased from 19 million in 1990 to 33 million in 2013. In 2016, the DALYS associated with CKD alongside other co-morbidities such as HTN, DM and cancer were found to increase significantly between 1990-2015.³ In patient with renal dysfunction, the renal excretion of the parent drug and its metabolite is already impaired leading to accumulation and toxicity. Also, the plasma protein binding is reduced which in turn will affect the process such as distribution and elimination. The activities of drug metabolizing enzymes and drug transporter are also reduced. In renal impaired patient the medication dosing errors are the most important DRPs. Majorly, older patients are at the higher risk of developing advanced disease and related adverse effects due to increased age and presence of polypharmacy because of many co morbidities. Drug elimination with the help of kidneys correlates with the GFR. Therefore, it is logical to use GFR for adjusting the dosage in CKD patients.⁴ To calculate the GFR of the individual patient, MDRD formula gives the more accurate results as compared to Cockcroft- Gault formula (CG). The CG formula overestimates the results. Smallest mean bias and highest accuracy is seen in MDRD formula.⁵ The major changes in ADME in patients with CKD are given in following table:

Table 1: Pharmacokinetic parameters of CKD patients.⁶

Parameters	Significant Changes
Absorption	Poorly quantified, it may increase or decrease
Distribution	No changes or increase
Metabolism	Decrease
Elimination	Decrease

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY DESIGN AND POPULATION

This was an Observational and retrospective study with 110 population size.

STUDY DURATION

The total duration for the study was 3 months and 2 months for data analysis and data compilation.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in accordance with the ICH-GCP guidelines. The important documents such as protocol, data collection form like ICF, CRF was presented to the Ethics committee for approval of the same. The study proceeded after the permission was granted. This study was designed as a retrospective and observational. This was conducted at tertiary care hospital for inpatients who has been diagnosed with CKD stage 3, 4, and 5 in the previous year from January 2020-January 2021. The main aim was to determine the accuracy of the Antimicrobial, Antihypertensive and oral hypoglycemic agents dosage in the patients diagnosed with CKD.

PROCEDURE

To start the study, the permission was taken from the MRD department of the hospital to access the file of the previous year and particularly of those patients who were diagnosed with CKD stage 3, 4, and 5. Once the permission was granted, the study was initiated by collecting the necessary data from the patient's case sheet into Case Report Form. The data collection included Patients demographic details, vital parameters, Medication chart information, Lab reports with special focus on Sr. Cr. and GFR. From the CRF, using the value of Sr. Cr., and patients age GFR was calculated by the MDRD equation. The calculated GFR helped to determine the actual dose that should be given to the particular patient. The "The Renal Drug Handbook – The ultimate Prescribing guide for Renal practitioner" was referred to check the dose according to the GFR of the individual subject. Statistical analysis was carried out by finding the mean and determining the percentage. The result of the study stated the percentage of the population with irrational Antimicrobial prescription and which of the prescribed antimicrobials has the highest number of the improper prescribed dose. On the basis of the statistics, a final conclusion was made which concluded the drugs requiring dose adjustment.

STUDY CRITERIA

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients who have been diagnosed with CKD stage 3, 4 and 5.
- CKD patients with any co-morbid conditions.
- Patients prescribed with Antimicrobials, Antihypertensive and Oral hypoglycemic agents.
- Adult patients with age more than 18.
- Both male and female patients.
- Daycare patients who have been to dialysis treatment.

Exclusion Criteria

- Pediatric Patients.
- Patient who have been diagnosed with Cancer, AKI, and SARS- COVID-19.
- Pregnant women and lactating mothers.
- Patient diagnosed with CKD stage 1 and 2.
- Patient with Kidney transplantation.

RESULTS

Socio-demographic characteristics

Based on inclusion criteria, a total 110 patients with CKD were identified during our study period. Majority of the patients are male. Table 2 summarizes the data regarding the gender of the study Patients.

Table 2: Demographic characteristics of study patients.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	70	63.6%
Female	40	36.4%
Total	110	100%

The study population consisted of 70 (63.6%) males and 40 (36.4%) females. Mean age of the male patients is 61.6 ± 16.6 and Mean age of the female patients is 58 ± 17.7 .

Figure 1: Bar Graph - Gender distribution.

Figure 2: Ratio of Gender.

Table 3: Demographic characteristic of the study patients.

AgeCategory(years)	Frequency	Percentage
18-30	09	8.2%
31-45	04	3.6%
46-65	65	59.1%
>65	32	29.1%
Total	110	100%

Majority of the patients were in a range of 46-65 years. There were 65 patients whose age was in range of 46-65. And 32 patients were >65 years of age.

Figure3: Bar-chart representation of patient's age.

Figure 4: Pie chart- Patient's age in percentage.

Evaluation of renal function

The mean Sr. Cr. Value of the 110 CKD patients was 7.94 ± 4.65 . All of the CKD patients were categorized according to CKD stage based on GFR value. Table 4 summarizes the total number of patients in each stage of CKD.

Table 4: Clinical characteristic of the study patients.

GFR(ml/min/1.73m2)	CKDstage	Totalnumberofpatients
30-59	03	05(4.5%)
15-29	04	09(8.2%)
<15	05(ESRD)	96(87.3%)

Out of 110 patients 96 (87.3%) had CKD stage 5, 09 (8.2%) patients had CKD stage 4 and 05 (4.5%) had CKD stage 3.

Figure5: Bar graph- Stages of CKD.

Figure 6: Pie chart - Stages of CKD.

Evaluation of prescribed drugs

A total 361 orders of our study medication list were prescribed. Among this, there were antihypertensive drugs, oral hypoglycemic agents and antimicrobial drugs too. Table 5 includes total number of drugs that were prescribed to the patients.

Table 5: Number of prescribed drugs.

Antihypertensive	199(55.12%)
Oral Hypoglycemic	53(14.68%)
Antimicrobial	109(30.19%)
Total Drug Prescribed	361

Figure 7: Bar graph- Drug Classes.

Figure 8: Pie chart- Drug classes in percentage.

Evaluation of renal dosing adjustment

Table 6 summarizes the total number of orders of each drug or drug class, with the counts and corresponding percentages of orders that were adjusted adequately, not adjusted and contradicted drugs.

Table 6: List of medication and their adjustment rates.

Class	Not Adjusted	Contraindicated	Adjusted
Antihypertensive (199)	03 (1.5%)	00	196 (98.5%)
Oral hypoglycemics (53)	04 (7.55%)	08 (15.1%)	41 (77.4%)
Antimicrobials (109)	18 (16.5%)	00	91 (83.5%)

Figure 9: List of medicines, adjusted medicines, and contraindicated medicines.

Antihypertensive Drugs:

The result showed that majority 196 (98.5%) of the antihypertensive drugs were adjusted appropriately. And total 03 (1.5%) drugs out of 199 were not adjusted appropriately according to renal impairment of the patient.

Figure 10: Adjustment rates of Anti-Hypertensive agents.

Oral Hypoglycemic Agents:

The result showed that majority 41 (77.4%) of the oral hypoglycemic drugs were adjusted appropriately. And total 04 (7.55%) drugs out of 53 were not adjusted appropriately according to renal impairment of the patient, whereas 08 (15.1%) drugs were contraindicated and given to patients.

Figure 11: Adjustment rates of Oral hypoglycemic agents.

Antimicrobial Drugs:

The result showed that majority 91 (83.5%) of the antimicrobial drugs were adjusted appropriately. And total 18 (16.5%) drugs out of 109 were not adjusted appropriately according to renal impairment of the patient.

Figure 12: Adjustment rates of Anti-Microbial agents.

DISCUSSION

Our study was designed as retrospective study and we included the data of 110 patients from the time period of January 2020- January 2021. The study was conducted to observe the inappropriateness in dosing of the Anti-hypertensive, Oral Hypoglycemic and Anti-microbial in CKD patients. In our study we included both male and female patients diagnosed with CKD stage 3, 4 and 5. The selection criteria was limited for stage 3, 4 and 5 as in patients diagnosed with CKD stage 1 and 2 dose adjustment is not required. Total number of patients enrolled in the study was 110. The total number of the Anti-Hypertensive, Oral Hypoglycemic and Anti-microbial prescribed were 361. The major drug category prescribed was Anti-hypertensive 199 (55.12%), followed by Anti-Microbial 109 (30.19%), followed by OHA 53 (14.68%). Dose of 328 out of 361 drugs were prescribed appropriately. Still Adjustment was required in all of the three classes of drugs with majorly in Antimicrobials 18 (16.5%) followed by OHA 04 (7.55%) followed by anti-hypertensive 03 (1.5%). Overall the adjustment was required in 25 prescribed drugs. Apart from these, the patients were also prescribed with the drugs that are contraindicated in CKD stage 3, 4, and 5.

The total number of the drugs contraindicated were 8 which were all OHA contributing 15% to the contraindicated category. From Anti-hypertensive, total 3 drugs required adjustment. Those are Nifedipine, Metolazone and Nebivolol (1 time each). From OHA total 4 drugs required dose adjustment. Those are Gliclazide (2 times), Gliclazide+Metformin (1 time) and Sitagliptin (1 time). The contraindicated drugs were Voglibose (4 times), Glyburide (3 times) and Gliclazide+ Metformin (1 time). From Antimicrobial drugs total 18 drugs required dose adjustment. Those were Meropenem (8 times), Levofloxacin, Cefexime and Hydroxychloroquine (2 times each) whereas Ceftriaxone, Ofloxacin, Ofloxacin + Ornidazole and Rifaximin (1 time each) were adjusted inappropriately.

CONCLUSION

There were total 110 files collected from MRD department of Kiran Multi Super Speciality Hospital and Research Center, Surat of CKD patients. The male to female ratio was 70:40. The mean age was 60.28. 17.1. All these patients were categorized into CKD stage 3, 4, and 5 by calculating the GFR using MDRD formula. There were 5, 9, and 96 patients categorized in stage CKD stage 3, 4 and 5 respectively. The mean serum creatinine was found to be 7.94. 4.65. The total prescription drugs given to 110 patients were 361 out of which 199 were Anti-Hypertensive, 53 were OHA, and 109 were Anti-microbial. 3 Anti-Hypertensive drugs required dose adjustment. All the three drugs are Nebivolol, Metolazone, and Nifedipine. 18 Anti-microbial drugs required dose adjustment. Majorly the adjustment was required in Meropenem. 4 OHA required dose adjustment and 8 OHA were contraindicated. Majorly the adjustment was required in Gliclazide. Also, Gliclazide + Metformin, Glyburide, Voglibose should be discontinued in the patients as these 3 drugs were contraindicated. Out of 361 prescribed drugs, the dose of 328 drugs was already adjusted by the physician, so no further adjustment was required.

Recommend Future Research : To assess the appropriate dosing of Chemotherapeutic agents, Cardiovascular agents and NSAIDs in CKD patients.

ABBREVIATION

AMA- Anti-microbial agents;
AHA- Antihypertensive agents;
OHA- Oral Hypoglycemic Agents
CKD- Chronic Kidney Disease;
GFR- Glomerular Filtration Rate;
MDRD- Modification of Diet in Renal Disease;
ESRD- End Stage Renal Disease;
Sr.Cr- Serum Creatinine;
DM- Diabetes Mellitus;
HTN- Hypertension;
CVD- Cardiovascular Disease;
HIV- Human Immunodeficiency Virus;
BP- Blood Pressure; **ACEI** s- Angiotensin Converting Enzyme Inhibitors;
ARB s- Angiotensin-II Receptor Blockers;
DALYS- Disability-adjusted Life Year;
DRP s- Drug Related Problems;
MDRD- Modification of Diet in Renal Disease;
CG- Cockcroft-Gault formula;
ADME- Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion;
ICH-GCP- International Council of Harmonisation- Good Clinical Practice;
ICF- Informed Consent Form; **CRF-** Case Report Form

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

Richa, Fatmabibi and Khushboo for designing and conducting study, analyzing data, interpreting result and drafting manuscript.

Dr. Pankaj and Dr. Kalpesh were involved in supervision of study and its critical review. Final approval of the version to be published is given by all the authors.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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